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WETLANDS WITHIN A MEDITERRANEAN NATURAL PARK

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Abstract: The contribution of plankton in the performance of three constructed wetlands (CWs) within the Albufera de València Natural Park has been analyzed, taxonomic group by group, over a two-year operation period in the different sectors of each CW: horizontal subsurface-flow -A-, free-water surface -B- and lagoons -C-. Tancat de la Pipa CW (TPCW) only contains B-C sectors, while the others have all three types. Treatment efficiency of each sector type on the taxonomic groups was evaluated by calculating frequency of phytoplankton reduction (zooplankton production), mass removal (production) efficiencies and rates, and accumulated removed phytoplankton mass (produced zooplankton mass). The phytoplankton biomass entering Tancat de Mília CW (TMCW) was significantly higher ($47 \pm 22 \text{ mm}^3 \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$) than in the other CWs (10 ± 11 , $6 \pm 5 \text{ mm}^3 \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$), but the outlets did not show significant differences. 7574 and 180 kgDW were eliminated during the two-year period in TMCW and Tancat de L'Illa CW (TLICW), from which 72% and 91% were removed cyanobacteria. Conversely, 470 kgDW of phytoplankton were produced in TPCW, but 99 kg of cyanobacteria eliminated. Mean efficiencies in zooplankton production were 682%, 157% and 112% in TLICW, TMCW and TPCW. There were evident spring production peaks of cladocerans in all CWs. Ostracods were much more abundant in the B sectors (related to the high density of emergent vegetation). In TMCW, the removal efficiencies were significantly higher during the second operation year. These CWs have undergone changes in the composition of phytoplankton and zooplankton communities, both spatially and temporally, which represent an improvement in the water quality which is returned to the eutrophic main lagoon within the Natural Park. We do not recommend using only chlorophyll and phycocyanin measurements as a surrogate of phytoplankton and cyanobacterial biomass. Instead, this can be considered only as a complement to the traditional analyses of microalgae and cyanobacterial presence.

**PLANKTON PARTICIPATION IN THE PERFORMANCE OF THREE
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22 TPCW. There were evident spring production peaks of cladocerans in all CWs. Ostracods were
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24 TMCW, the removal efficiencies were significantly higher during the second operation year.
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26 communities, both spatially and temporally, which represent an improvement in the water

27 quality which is returned to the eutrophic main lagoon within the Natural Park. We do not
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29 phytoplankton and cyanobacterial biomass. Instead, this can be considered only as a
30 complement to the traditional analyses of microalgae and cyanobacterial presence.

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35 **1. Introduction**

36 Most wetlands are endangered worldwide by excessive nutrient contents caused by cultural
37 eutrophication (Verhoeven, 2014). This water deterioration compromises their ecosystem
38 services linked to biodiversity (Vymazal, 2011). The use of green infrastructures such as
39 constructed wetlands (CWs) located close to natural wetlands is nowadays growing, as an
40 effort to recover the lost services wetlands provide. CWs efficiently remove suspended
41 material, microalgae and nutrients from water (Chen et al., 2011; Dong et al., 2011; Travaini-
42 Lima et al., 2016). All this has as a consequence establishing better water conditions (increased
43 transparency, submerged vegetation recovery, etc.) and, therefore, enhanced biodiversity
44 occurs (Vymazal, 2011; Martín et al., 2013; Rodrigo et al., 2013a, b; Land et al., 2016).
45 Hernández-Crespo et al. (2017) have mainly analyzed the results on hydrology and physical
46 and chemical variables obtained from a two-year water quality monitoring program (2014-15)
47 in the frame of a “science-based governance” of CWs in the LIFE + 12 Albufera project. This
48 project is focused on demonstrating how three CWs can be managed, integrating multiple
49 objectives: (i) the reduction of pollutants from a hypereutrophic lagoon, l'Albufera de València,
50 a Ramsar and Natura 2000 site; (ii) the recovery of the lost habitats in the natural park it
51 belongs to, improving biodiversity both inside and outside the CWs, and (iii) for sustainable

52 and participatory public use. In the paper, it was reported how the results of the relationships
53 among hydraulic operation and physical and chemical variables in two different CWs
54 typologies (five free-water surface CW sectors and one horizontal subsurface flow CW sector)
55 show that the CWs were capable of improving the water quality, but showing clear differences
56 depending on the type of CW. One of these free-water surface CWs (Tancat de la Pipa -TPCW
57 hereafter-) has been operating and studied since 2009 (Martín et al., 2013; Rodrigo et al.,
58 2013a,b; Calero et al., 2015). As all of these authors and others (Li et al., 2014; Guo et al.,
59 2016) have already suggested, biological enhancement, in terms of zooplankton biomass
60 (particularly cladocerans), is a key variable in the restoration of eutrophic waters in these kinds
61 of systems. At the same time, clear shifts in phytoplankton composition towards a more
62 desirable community structure have already been observed in the waters of TPCW; for
63 example, the reduction of potentially toxic cyanobacteria (Rodrigo et al., 2013a). This time, the
64 study of three full scale CWs located relatively close to each other, influenced by similar but
65 not exactly the same factors, represents an invaluable opportunity to find similarities and
66 differences in plankton performance in order to detect patterns in the functioning of these
67 aquatic systems. Moreover, as already carried out for TPCW (Calero et al., 2017), we have
68 applied methods typically used only with nutrients when referring to CWs treatment
69 efficiencies to plankton variables, such as the calculation of cumulative mass removal and
70 production. Some studies have described plankton communities in CWs (Luyiga and Kiwanuka,
71 2003; Chen et al., 2011; Li et al., 2014; Travaini-Lima et al., 2016). However, none of them
72 show results concerning cumulative planktonic mass removal and production.

73 On occasion, photosynthetic pigments have been evaluated as a surrogate of phytoplankton
74 biomass (Kasprzak et al., 2008; Ramaraj et al., 2013) as simpler and more objective methods to
75 replace the traditional cell counting technique in natural waters, and for a reduction in
76 management costs. Recently, Canfield et al. (2019) concluded that if resources are limited,
77 chlorophyll is recommended for monitoring long-term trends in lakes because it provides an

78 estimate of biomass magnitude. Related to this, several studies have been published proposing
79 the measurement of *in vivo* phycocyanin (a photosynthetic accessory pigment) fluorescence as
80 an early warning or alert system for cyanobacteria presence especially in reservoir intake
81 waters (Ahn et al., 2007; Brient et al., 2008 and references therein). These methods have
82 proven to be appropriate under such circumstances. However, some questions can be posed:
83 are these methods suitable for other kinds of aquatic environments, for example wetlands, or,
84 as in this case, for CWs? Up to what limit (in terms of cyanobacteria biomass) might this
85 method be used in a reliable way?

86 Therefore, we have analyzed, in detail, the participation of plankton in the performance of
87 three CWs, and the specific objectives of this study are: (1) to analyze if chlorophyll *a* and *in*
88 *vivo* phycocyanin can be effectively used as a substitute for counting phytoplankton; (2) to
89 evaluate the removal frequencies, efficiencies and rates of phytoplankton; (3) to quantify the
90 production (or reduction) of the different zooplanktonic groups, and (4) to allow a comparison
91 of the different types of CWs and the different sectors within them in relation to the
92 contribution of plankton to eutrophication remediation.

93 **2. Material and methods**

94 *2.1. Study sites and CWs characteristics*

95 The study sites are three CWs, which were former rice fields, placed within the Albufera de
96 València Natural Park (Spain), a wetland of international importance (Hernández-Crespo et al.,
97 2017). It mainly consists of the Albufera de València lagoon, a hypereutrophic (current annual
98 mean chlorophyll *a* of approximately 100 µg L⁻¹) large lagoon (2,100 ha surface), surrounded
99 by 14,000 ha of fields devoted to rice cultivation. The Natural Park was subjected to high
100 urban, agricultural and industrial pressure. The three CWs are *Tancat de la Pipa*, 40 ha (TPCW
101 hereafter), *Tancat de Mília*, 33.4 ha (TMCW hereafter) and *Tancat de L'Illa*, 16 ha (TLICW
102 hereafter) (Fig. 1S). The three CWs have different combinations of free-water surface CWs
103 (sector B) and two of them have an area of horizontal subsurface flow CWs (sector A), and

104 operate at different hydraulic loads and water depths. The three CWs also have shallow
105 lagoons located at the end of the system (sector C). The incoming water, in the case of TPCW
106 and TMCW, is hypereutrophic water from the Albufera de València lagoon and, in the case of
107 TLICW, from a small lagoon that drains the irrigation water from the rice fields. After crossing
108 the CWs, the water is returned to the main lagoon. The water flows from the inlet to sectors A,
109 B and finally, C, except in TPCW, where there is no sector A. For further details on the study
110 sites see Hernández-Crespo et al. (2017).

111 *2.2. Sample collection and plankton determination*

112 Water samples were collected seasonally from January 2014 to December 2015: each year,
113 one sampling was performed in winter, three samplings in spring (March, April and May), as
114 this is the main season for the development of plankton in the Mediterranean region, one
115 sampling in summer (July) and one sampling in autumn (October). In each CW, four sampling
116 sites were chosen (the inlet, the outlet and two inner sites; Fig. 1S). In TPCW, sector B is
117 divided into two subsectors (fp and FG). Most samples were taken from the fp subsector, but
118 on a couple of occasions (July and October 2015) water samples were collected from the FG
119 subsector as the fp subsector had been dried for management reasons.

120 Unfiltered samples for phytoplankton counting were fixed with lugol and counted in Utermöhl
121 chambers with an inverted microscope (Olympus CK2) at 400 magnifications to obtain the
122 density. At least 400 individuals of the most abundant population were counted, implying a
123 10% error (Lund et al., 1958). Taxonomic determination was carried out using specific book
124 collections and reviews, such as *Archiv für Hydrobiologie (Algologische Studien)*, monographic
125 series of *Süßwasserflora von Mitteleuropa* (Gustav Fischer Verlag, Stuttgart) and *Das*
126 *Phytoplankton des Süßwassers* (Ed. Schweizerbart'sche Verlagsbuchhandlung) (more details in
127 Rojo et al., 2012). Algal biovolume was calculated with cell densities and cell volume,
128 measuring sizes from at least 20 individuals, and following Rott (1981) and Hillebrand et al.
129 (1999). For cumulative mass removal (see below), phytoplankton dry weight was obtained

130 from phytoplankton biovolume by assuming a cell density of 1 g cm^{-3} (Suthers et al., 2009) and
131 a wet/dry weight ratio of 10 (Chapra, 2008). Cumulative mass removal was expressed in
132 carbon units using the conversion of $\text{pg C cel}^{-1} = 0.216 \times \text{Biovol}(\mu\text{m}^3)^{0.939}$ for all microalgae
133 species, except for diatoms ($\text{pg C cel}^{-1} = 0.288 \times \text{Biovol}(\mu\text{m}^3)^{0.811}$) (Menden-Deuer and Lessard,
134 2000).

135 An autotrophy/mixotrophy ratio was calculated for each sampling date to relate the biovolume
136 of autotrophic groups (i.e. Chlorophyceae and Bacillariophyceae) with potential mixotrophic
137 ones (i.e. Cryptophyceae, Chrysophyceae, Dinophyceae and Euglenophyceae) (Rodrigo et al.,
138 2013a).

139 Water samples for metazooplankton were filtered through 45 mm Nyltal mesh and preserved
140 with a formalin solution (at 4% final concentration). Density was calculated by counting with
141 an inverted microscope (Olympus CK2) at 100 magnifications. Taxonomic determination and
142 biomass were obtained following the methods described in Rojo et al. (2012); the manuals
143 used for the identification of metazooplankton taxa were those of Dussart (1967, 1969), Koste
144 (1978), Segers (1995), Einsle (1996), Orlova-Bienkowskaja (2001) and Nogrady and Segers
145 (2002). For biomass determination, at least 20 individuals of each population were measured.
146 Rotifer and ostracod biovolumes were calculated assimilating body shapes to geometrical
147 bodies. Biovolume was converted to biomass assuming a body density of 1 g cm^{-3} . Crustacean
148 biomass was obtained with length-dry weight regressions and a 1/10 proportion for dry wet
149 weight. The cumulative mass production was expressed in carbon units using the conversion 1
150 $\text{g DW} = 0.4 \text{ g C}$ for Rotifera, Cladocera and Copepoda (Reiss and Schmid-Araya, 2008).

151 2.3. Pigment determination

152 Water samples were also analyzed for chlorophyll *a*, which was determined after filtration
153 with glass microfiber filters (Whatman GF/F, pore size 0.7 μm) and extraction with 90%
154 acetone (Rodrigo et al., 2013a). *In situ* fluorescence measurements were performed with an
155 AquafluorTM handheld fluorometer (Turner designs) in each sampling site, equipped with two

156 channels. One of the channels was used for the excitation of phycocyanin pigments (excitation:
157 595 nm; emission: 670 nm). Water samples (around 3 ml) were placed in 10 mm x 10 mm
158 polystyrene cuvettes, and each sample was measured at 3-4 replicates. Calibration of the
159 device was carried out with two unialgal laboratory cultures (*Microcystis aeruginosa* and
160 *Spirulina* sp.). A phycocyanin extract (SigmaAldrich) was also used for calibration. For routine
161 measurements, single-point and blank type fluorometer calibration was used. Distilled water
162 was used as a blank. For the single-point, a solid secondary standard (P/N 8000-952) was used.
163 This allows quick and easy checks of calibration, stability and performance. The minimum
164 detection level of the instrument is about 150 cells mL⁻¹. Samples with high cyanobacteria
165 densities were diluted for phycocyanin measurements.

166 *2.4. Data analysis: correlation between pigments and phytoplankton biomass, removal-*
167 *production calculations and statistics*

168 Linear regression analyses were performed between photosynthetic pigments (chlorophyll *a*
169 and phycocyanin) and the biovolume of total phytoplankton and cyanobacteria, respectively,
170 for each CW.

171 The frequency of reduction of phytoplankton biomass comparing sector B (or A+B) and sector
172 C (or production of zooplankton) was calculated as the number of dates when this happens,
173 comparing the inlets and outlets divided by the total number of sampling dates (12). The
174 treatment efficiency of each of the above-mentioned sectors was determined from inlet total
175 plankton (and the different taxonomic groups) mass loading, annual mass removal efficiencies
176 (%), and mass removal rates (mg DW plankton m⁻² d⁻¹). The inflow (L s⁻¹), the input plankton
177 concentration (mg L⁻¹), the rainfall flow (L s⁻¹) which can exert a dilution effect, the
178 evapotranspiration (L s⁻¹) which can exert a concentration effect, the output plankton
179 concentration (mg L⁻¹) and the wetland area (m²) were considered. These variables were
180 considered constant between measurements, except for precipitation, since this is highly
181 variable in this area. After the two-year period of operation, the accumulated removed mass of

182 phytoplankton was calculated for sector B (or A+B) and the overall CW for each CW: the
183 difference between cumulative inflow and outflow. The cumulative inflow mass load was
184 estimated considering time between sampling dates (in days). For zooplankton, accumulated
185 produced mass was calculated, this being the difference between the cumulative outflow and
186 inflow. For more details about calculations see Hernández-Crespo et al. (2017).
187 Comparisons of means of the different plankton variables between the CWs, and between
188 sectors within each CW, were made with repeated ANOVA tests when normality and
189 homoscedasticity were accomplished. *Post hoc* Tukey's pairwise comparisons were performed
190 afterwards. Otherwise, non-parametric tests were used (Mann-Whitney two-samples). To
191 detect seasonality (intra-annual and interannual), Pearson (or Spearman) correlation
192 coefficients were determined between plankton variables. All statistical analyses were
193 executed using the statistical package IBM SPSS 19.0.

194 **3. Results and discussion**

195 *3.1. Planktonic biomass*

196 *3.1.1. Phytoplankton biomass*

197 The total phytoplankton two-year mean biomass entering TMCW was significantly higher ($47 \pm$
198 $22 \text{ mm}^3 \text{ L}^{-1}$) than in the other two CWs ($10 \pm 11 \text{ mm}^3 \text{ L}^{-1}$ in TPCW and $6 \pm 5 \text{ mm}^3 \text{ L}^{-1}$ in TLICW;
199 Fig. 1A, Table 1). This difference is explained by the different origins of incoming waters:
200 TMCW inputs are purely Albufera de València lagoon waters from its southern part, TPCW
201 inputs are also Albufera de València lagoon waters, but from the northern part and combined
202 with waters arriving at this lagoon through one channel and a gully which discharge upstream
203 waters, and finally TLICW is fed with water from a small lagoon that drains the irrigation water
204 from rice fields, with a much lower phytoplankton concentration. Only the cyanobacteria,
205 diatoms and chlorophyte biomass in the inlets was significantly higher in TMCW (Table 1S). In
206 spite of the higher total phytoplankton biomass in the TPCW outlet, the two-year annual
207 means were not statistically different among the three CWs. Only the biomass of

208 cyanobacteria was significantly higher in the TMCW outlet (mean of $2.2 \text{ mm}^3 \text{ L}^{-1}$) compared to
209 the outlets of TPCW and TLICW (means of 0.4 and $0.7 \text{ mm}^3 \text{ L}^{-1}$, respectively).

210 In the inlets of the three CWs, the total phytoplankton mean biomass was similar in the two
211 studied years (Fig. 1A; F_{ANOVA} and p-values in Table 1), and this also occurred with the different
212 taxonomic groups (Table 1S). The only exception was the mean cryptophyte biomass in the
213 TMCW inlet in 2015, which was half the mean of 2014. Overall, no repeated seasonal
214 dynamics, comparing 2014 and 2015, were found in any site in each of the CWs (see r_s and p-
215 values in Tables 1 and 1S). Only in the TMCW outlet was total phytoplankton significantly
216 lower in 2015, changing from a mean of 7 to $3 \text{ mm}^3 \text{ L}^{-1}$, and the cyanobacteria were
217 significantly reduced from 4 to $1 \text{ mm}^3 \text{ L}^{-1}$ from 2014 to 2015. However, some of the potentially
218 toxic cyanobacteria were found with slightly higher densities in 2015, but in no case were their
219 densities so high as to cause environmental or health problems. The low concentrations of
220 potential toxic cyanobacteria found during 2014-2015 in the three CWs are similar to the ones
221 found in the small lagoons (sector C) of TPCW in previous periods (Rodrigo et al., 2013a), and
222 they are below the toxicity limit of $2 \text{ mm}^3 \text{ L}^{-1}$ established for the Albufera de València lagoon
223 (Romo et al., 2013). Moreover, there was a clear relationship between cyanobacteria biomass
224 in the inlet and sector B in TPCW, which is not apparent in sector C (Table 1S). This significant
225 correlation was not found in TMCW or TLICW. In both cases, the presence of the subsurface
226 flow sector A, absent in TPCW, strongly modified the content of phytoplankton in sector B,
227 there being a weak relationship between the phytoplankton leaving sector A with the
228 phytoplankton in the inlet waters. TLICW had no significant differences in mean phytoplankton
229 biomass when comparing years, sites and seasonality. In other studies of the few considering
230 plankton performance in constructed wetlands (Chen et al., 2011), phytoplankton differed
231 significantly among but not within the different study wetlands.

232

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234 3.1.2. Zooplankton biomass

235 The total zooplankton mean biomass entering TMCW was also significantly higher (290 ± 187
236 $\mu\text{g DW L}^{-1}$) than in the other two CWs ($124 \pm 101 \mu\text{g DW L}^{-1}$ in TPCW and $92 \pm 51 \mu\text{g DW L}^{-1}$ in
237 TLICW; Fig. 1B, F_{ANOVA} and p-values in Table 1). This difference was caused mainly by
238 cladocerans (Table 2S), indicating that the waters from the southern part of Albufera de
239 València lagoon are richer in this group. In the outlet, the zooplankton biomass was statistically
240 greater only in TLICW with respect to TPCW, in this case caused by the biomass of copepods.
241 Ostracod biomass was lower in TMCW compared to TPCW.

242 As happened with phytoplankton in the three CWs, the total zooplankton mean biomass (and
243 that of the taxonomic groups) in the inlet was similar in the two studied years (Fig. 1B; see
244 F_{ANOVA} and p-values, Tables 1 and 2S). However, the seasonal dynamics of total zooplankton
245 biomass was not the same in 2014 compared to 2015 in each of the CWs (r_s and p-values in
246 Table 1), with the exception of the cladoceran biomass in both the inlet and outlet of TMCW,
247 which showed significant correlations caused by peaks of this group during spring in both years
248 (Table 2S).

249 Similar to what happened with cyanobacteria in TPCW, there was a clear relationship between
250 total zooplankton biomass in the inlet and sector B of this CW (F_{ANOVA} and p-value, Table 1),
251 which did not occur in the outlets after the water had passed through sector C, and this
252 pattern was caused mainly by the copepod biomass (Table 2S). The change of cladoceran
253 biomass throughout this CW was more internal, not dependent on the inlet; the same
254 occurred with the ostracods (r_s and p-value in Table 2S). No correlation in total zooplankton
255 biomass was found between the different sites in TMCW or TLICW (Table 1), and the
256 explanation again can be found due to the existence of the subsurface flow in sector A.

257 In general terms, there was a seasonal replacement of zooplanktonic taxonomic groups
258 observed during this study in TPCW, typical of Mediterranean wetlands (copepod dominance
259 in winter interrupted by the spring bloom of cladocerans, and the dominance of rotifers in

260 summer and autumn; Rojo and Rodrigo, 2010). This pattern had been detected previously in
261 this CW (Rodrigo et al., 2013a; Calero et al., 2015) and it has now been confirmed for the other
262 two CWs. However, Travaini-Lima et al. (2016) found that rotifers were always the dominant
263 group in both the dry and wet seasons and sampling sites in tropical constructed wetlands but
264 copepods and cladocerans were more abundant during the rainy than during the dry season.
265 Chen et al. (2011) again found significant differences in zooplankton among but not within the
266 different study wetlands.

267 *3.2. Relationship between pigments and phytoplankton biomass*

268 The relationship between chlorophyll *a* and phytoplankton biovolume was statistically
269 significant in the three CWs (Fig. 2A). However, the relationship was different in TMCW, with a
270 much higher slope. Considering the same range of chlorophyll and biovolume for each CW (up
271 to 60 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ and 20 $\text{mm}^3 \text{L}^{-1}$) where we find most of the data, most of the points corresponding
272 to TPCW are below the regression line, while the majority of the points of the other two CWs
273 are located above the line (Fig. 2A). This implies that the particular composition of
274 phytoplankton in each CWs yields a precise relationship of photosynthetic pigments and
275 microalgal biovolume, which is, in turn, related to the autotrophic or mixotrophic metabolism
276 of phytoplankton organism (Saad et al., 2016). The autotrophy/heterotrophy ratio was much
277 higher in the inlet, and also in the first part of sector B of TMCW, due to the high biomass of
278 cyanobacteria (Fig. 2B). Phycocyanin, the most common phycobilin in cyanobacteria of shallow
279 freshwaters (Stockner et al., 2000), was only significantly correlated with the biovolume of
280 cyanobacteria in the case of the higher values of both variables in the inlet of TMCW (Fig. 3).
281 On the other hand, the relationship of the pigment and the cyanobacteria biomass was
282 different in TPCW compared to TLICW: in the former, higher values of phycocyanin
283 corresponded to low biomasses, and in the latter, low values of the pigment corresponded to a
284 higher cyanobacterial biomass (Fig. 3). Again, depending on the particular composition of the
285 community, these relationships are clearly different. The type of cyanobacteria (unicellular,

286 colonial or filamentous organisms) and the real phycobilin composition (phycoerythrin-rich
287 cyanobacteria could also be present, Vörös et al., 2009), or even the presence of the other
288 phytoplankton group known to contain phycobiliproteins, i.e. cryptophytes (Downes and Hall,
289 1998), which were quite abundant in some samples of the CWs, might be the main causes of
290 the lack of a good correlation between the two kinds of determination carried out. Kasprzak et
291 al. (2008) and Ramaraj et al. (2013) recognized that chlorophyll is not an accurate
292 measurement of phytoplankton biomass. Therefore, we support this conclusion and we do not
293 recommend using only chlorophyll *a* and *in vivo* phycocyanin measurements as a surrogate of
294 phytoplankton and cyanobacterial biomass for CWs. Instead, they can be considered only as a
295 complement to the traditional analyses of microalgae and cyanobacterial presence. Therefore,
296 managers should integrate pigment determinations with microalgal biovolume measurements,
297 particularly if they are concerned about changing algal population dynamics and the presence
298 of cyanobacteria and mixotrophic phytoplankton.

299 *3.3. Phytoplankton removal frequencies, efficiencies and rates*

300 Removal frequencies, comparing the phytoplankton biomass in the inlets and the outlets, were
301 different among the CWs (Table 2): TMCW showed the highest frequency taking into account
302 the whole system, because in all the samplings the microalgal biomass at the outlet was lower
303 than at the inlet, and considering only sectors A+B the frequency was slightly lower; TPCW had
304 a removal frequency of 67% for the whole system, which was higher if only sector B was taken
305 into account; in TLICW, the frequency was the lowest, observing microalgal removal in only
306 50% of samplings, and there were no differences with regard to the whole system, or only in
307 sectors A+B. This means that sector C (the lagoons at the end of the system) played a different
308 role in each CW. In the case of TMCW, the lagoon improved removal efficiencies, in TPCW it
309 worsened them and in TLICW it had no effect. These differences might be related to the
310 presence of one island and several areas with emergent vegetation in the case of TMCW, so it
311 is less affected by wind resuspension; as for TPCW, in spite of it having two islands, the lower

312 hydraulic load rate and higher hydraulic retention time (Hernández-Crespo et al., 2017) must
313 have favored phytoplankton growth; the TLICW lagoon does not have any islands.

314 Regarding the reduction efficiencies of total phytoplankton, the two-year means in both TPCW
315 and TLICW were negative (Table 3) and statistically different from the positive mean of TMCW
316 (Table 4). In TPCW, only sector B had positive removal efficiencies. No seasonal correlation (r_s)
317 in reduction efficiencies among the CWs was found (Table 4). For the overall systems, the
318 mean reduction rate (Table 5) was maximal in TMCW ($74 \text{ mg DW m}^{-2}\text{d}^{-1}$) and minimum in
319 TPCW ($0.1 \text{ mg DW m}^{-2}\text{d}^{-1}$). In terms of cumulative mass reduction, 7574 kg DW and 180 kg DW
320 of phytoplankton were eliminated during the two-year period in TMCW and TLICW,
321 respectively, and, conversely, 470 kg DW of total phytoplankton were produced in TPCW.

322 Moreover, in none of the three CWs was a difference in the mean reduction efficiencies of
323 2014 compared to 2015 found. Only in TPCW was a seasonal pattern repeated each year, with
324 the production of total phytoplankton from the end of summer, autumn and winter, and a
325 reduction on the rest of the sampled dates, particularly in spring. The high nutrient
326 concentrations in water and sediment (Hernández-Crespo et al., 2017), together with the lack
327 of submerged vegetation in the small lagoons (sector C), the high temperatures in the warm
328 season and the elevated hours of sun in the geographic position of the site caused sector C to
329 act as a producer rather than a reducer of phytoplankton during this period.

330 Studying phytoplankton removal group by group, the frequency of cyanobacterial reduction
331 was 100% in TMCW and in sector B of TPCW. Only in TMCW were the removal efficiencies
332 significantly higher during the second year of operation (Table 2). Taking into account the two-
333 year period, cumulative cyanobacterial mass reduction was 99, 5473 and 163 Kg DW in TPCW,
334 TMCW and TLICW, respectively (Fig. 4) (~40, 1717 and 63 Kg C). The overall diatom reduction
335 frequency ranged from 75% (in TPCW and TLICW) to 92% (in TMCW). Removal shows similar
336 significant seasonal patterns in TPCW and TLICW (production in January, summer and autumn
337 2014 and a reduction in all seasons in 2015), but the mean reduction efficiency is statistically

338 higher in TMCW compared to TPCW and TLICW in sector B (or A+B). Cumulative diatom mass
339 reduction was 41, 1517 and 80 Kg DW in TPCW, TMCW and TLICW, respectively (~8, 140 and
340 13 Kg C). The overall chlorophyte reduction frequency was as low as 33% in TPCW and 100% in
341 TMCW, and the mean removal efficiency was positive only in TMCW, and therefore
342 significantly higher. No seasonality between each CWs was observed, but, again, there was a
343 significantly higher reduction in chlorophytes in TMCW during the second year of operation.
344 Cumulative chlorophyte mass reduction was 570 Kg DW (~205 Kg C) in TMCW, and 2 and 22 Kg
345 were produced in TPCW and TLICW, respectively. Only TPCW showed cryptophyte reduction
346 frequencies higher than 80% considering all sectors, and it was the only CW to generate
347 positive removal efficiencies; cryptophyte production was statistically much higher in TLICW
348 (Table 2). Cumulative cryptophyte mass reduction was 6 Kg DW in TPCW, with a cumulative
349 mass production of 77 and 866 Kg DW in TMCW and TLICW, respectively. Finally,
350 euglenophytes had negative reduction efficiencies in the three CWs (Table 3S) with no
351 statistical differences (Table 4S), but the mean reduction rates were positive, although close to
352 0 in TPCW and TMCW; seasonality was only observed between TPCW and TMCW (they had
353 large production peaks mainly at the same time, summer 2014 and autumn 2015). In terms of
354 cumulative reduction or production for the two-year period, 1 and 28 kg DW were reduced in
355 TPCW and TMCW, respectively, but 51 Kg DW were produced in TLICW (Fig. 4).
356 TMCW and TLICW were created shortly before the monitoring included in this study, therefore
357 it is not possible to compare them with the previous situation, unlike TPCW which was created
358 in 2008, with monitoring starting in 2009. The removal rate of total phytoplankton in sector B
359 in TPCW in 2014-2015 is much lower ($40 \text{ mg m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$) than that found during the first year of
360 operation ($151 \text{ mg m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$; Calero et al., 2015), but much higher than for the second and third
361 years of operation, when the rates were negative (-26 and $-47 \text{ mg m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$; Calero et al., 2015).
362 Macrophytes in CWs have a strong influence on the structure and dynamics of the

363 phytoplankton community, since their coverage is a major factor strongly modifying light
364 conditions (Travaini-Lima et al., 2016). During the first year, the coverage of emergent
365 vegetation (mainly *Typha* spp.) was extensive, but it was harvested. The recovery of vegetation
366 was not as successful as expected, and this is why later rates were negative. However, in the
367 new period, vegetation was recovered (this time mainly with *Phragmites australis*) and the
368 removal rates increased again.

369 3.4. Zooplankton production frequencies, efficiencies and rates

370 In the overall systems, the production frequency of total zooplankton (Table 2) was maximum
371 in TLICW and minimum in TMCW. Regarding production efficiencies (Table 3), and in spite of
372 the two-year mean value of TLICW being much higher (682%) than the other two CWs (112%
373 and 157%), there were no statistical differences among them due to the large variability in
374 each studied date. No seasonal pattern between the three CWs was found, nor was there a
375 seasonal pattern in each CW between years (Table 4).

376 Studying zooplankton production group by group, in the case of cladocerans the production
377 frequency (Table 2) was not very different among the CWs, but the mean efficiencies were
378 much higher in TLICW (Table 5S); however, due to the high production on particular dates, the
379 differences were not statistically significant (Table 6S). Moreover, there was a clear significant
380 seasonality in the production of cladocerans in the three CWs, with the maxima in April (r_s ,
381 Table 6S). Every year in the spring, large blooms of cladocerans produce plentiful amounts of
382 resting eggs which enrich the sediment bank to densities as high as 2.8 ± 0.3 ephippia cm^{-2} for
383 example in TPCW (unpublished results), waiting for hatching in the next spring
384 (Vandekerkhove et al., 2005). In sector B (or A+B) the mean production rates varied between a
385 minimum of $0.8 \text{ mg DW m}^{-2}\text{d}^{-1}$ for TLICW and a maximum of $4 \text{ mg DW m}^{-2}\text{d}^{-1}$ in TMCW (Table
386 8S); here, cumulative production reached 185 Kg DW at the end of sector C up to spring 2015
387 (Fig. 5). This accounted for 74 Kg of carbon produced internally in the system. In TLICW, the
388 production of cladocerans in sector C was high from spring of the second study year (more

389 than 230 Kg DW; 92 Kg of C). In TMCW, the increase in cladocerans was related with the higher
390 density of edible microalgae which substituted the cyanobacteria. Overall, the three CWs
391 received waters with smaller-size cladocerans and produced internally larger-size species with
392 greater grazing capacity (e.g. in TPCW *Chydorus sphaericus* in the inlet was substituted by
393 *Daphnia magna* in sector B; in the TMCW inlet *Moina micrura* and *Diaphanosoma*
394 *mongolianum* were substituted by *Ceriodaphnia reticulata* and several species of *Daphnia* (*D.*
395 *magna* represented more than 90% of biomass in spring 2015); in TLICW *D. magna* and *C.*
396 *reticulata* were exported from the system. This fact supports the observations of Guo et al.
397 (2016) who stressed how artificial aquatic food web systems not only efficiently removed
398 nutrients from sewage waters, but also increased the P-absorbance of *Daphnia*.

399 The production frequency of ostracods was higher in sectors B and A+B compared to the
400 system as a whole in the three CWs (Table 2). Ostracods were produced in the three CWs with
401 high mean efficiencies (Table 5S). In the fp subsector (sector B), a cumulative biomass of 55 Kg
402 DW of ostracods was produced at the end of the two-year study (Fig. 5). In the FG subsector
403 (sector B), the value was much lower, but in this case the data series is much shorter, these
404 results not being comparable. More than 20 Kg DW of cumulative biomass of ostracods in
405 sector B in TMCW were produced (Fig. 5). The increase in this group, mainly of benthic
406 features (Schmit et al., 2007), particularly in the B sectors, is clearly related to the type of
407 environment these sites provide: a high density of emergent vegetation compared to the C
408 sectors (lagoons) (Rodrigo et al., 2013a; Hernández-Crespo et al., 2017), therefore there is a
409 much greater surface for these organisms to live on, which may be carried along by the water
410 flow and hence be susceptible to being sampled at the outlets. This group has experienced an
411 important loss of biodiversity in western Mediterranean wetlands due to eutrophication and
412 pollution problems (Poquet et al., 2008; Valls et al., 2016); therefore, the development of this
413 group inside the CWs could help to turn this situation back to what it previously was.

414 The copepod production frequency for sectors A+B+C of TMCW was 0, which contrasts with
415 67% for the other two CWs (Table 2). Production efficiencies in this CW were statistically
416 different in comparison to the other two CWs (Tables 5S and 6S) because this group's biomass
417 is reduced rather than being increased. The removal of copepods in TMCW yielded an
418 accumulated value of 153 Kg DW for the two-year study, and the cumulative production of
419 copepods for TPCW and TLICW was 3 and 49 Kg DW, respectively. In the case of rotifers, the
420 production frequencies were the same for TPCW and TMCW for the whole system, but lower
421 than for TLICW (Table 2). Seasonality in the reduction efficiencies of both TMCW and TLICW
422 was observed over the two years, but the pattern was different among CWs. In TMCW, there
423 were clear production periods only in summer and at the beginning of autumn. In TLICW, there
424 were production peaks in March in both years; but in the second year the production peak in
425 summer was not observed. In the latter CW, rotifers were removed from the whole system by
426 7 Kg DW of cumulative mass (2.8 Kg C). Overall, a reduction in rotifers, rather than production,
427 might be interpreted as an improvement in water quality (Lodi et al., 2011; Jurczak et al.,
428 2019).

429 Most of the differences in zooplankton performance between sectors B and C are due to the
430 existence of emergent vegetation in the case of sectors B, versus open water practically
431 without submerged vegetation in the lagoons of the three CWs. On the other hand, the
432 differences between B sectors might be related to the type of emergent vegetation planted in
433 each case (Travaini-Lima et al., 2016). In TPCW, emergent plants existing in sector B were
434 mixed populations of *Phragmites australis*, *Typha angustifolia*, *Sparganium erectum* and *Iris*
435 *pseudacorus*, whereas in TMCW and TLICW they were mainly *Typha angustifolia*. Also, the
436 coverage of emergent vegetation was greater in TLICW (Hernández-Crespo et al., 2018).
437 Rodrigo et al. (2018) reported how the type of emergent vegetation (and its coverage)
438 influences the eutrophication reduction effect. The different kinds of emergent plants could

439 provide different surfaces onto which zooplankton diapausing eggs could be attached
440 (Gyllstrom and Hansson, 2004).

441 TPCW increased the percentage of production efficiencies of zooplankton in comparison to
442 previous studies (2009-2012), increasing from mean values of 65% in subsector FG of sector B
443 (Calero et al., 2015) or 75% in sector C (Rodrigo et al., 2013a) to more than 100%, both in the
444 CW as a whole, and in sector C. The mean production rate of total zooplankton in sector B (fp
445 subsector) in TPCW is slightly higher ($34 \text{ mg DW m}^{-2}\text{d}^{-1}$) than the one estimated for this sector
446 ($27 \text{ mg DW m}^{-2}\text{d}^{-1}$) in 2009-2012 (Calero et al., 2015). However, the large difference is due to
447 the highest production being in ostracod and copepod biomass, rather than the biomass of
448 cladocerans, which occurred in the previous period. Thus, the large grazers, the cladocerans,
449 have been partially substituted by the ostracods, which are also herbivores and detritivores, in
450 the role of the reduction of microalgae biomass. The aging of this CW resulted in important
451 changes in the zooplankton community structure. On the other hand, the comparison of
452 zooplankton between the inlet and the outlet of sector C (the lagoons) indicates a lower
453 production rate than that calculated for 2009-2012 ($2 \text{ mg DW m}^{-2}\text{d}^{-1}$; Rodrigo et al., 2013a). For
454 most of that period, the lagoon was characterized as possessing a wide coverage of submerged
455 vegetation, mainly *Myriophyllum spicatum* (Rodrigo et al., 2013b) but this disappeared in 2011
456 and despite efforts to recover it, this coverage never occurred again. The presence of this
457 vegetation clearly contributed to the development of large cladocerans, which could be hidden
458 from their predators within the submerged macrophytes (Burks et al., 2001). As stated by
459 Dong et al. (2011), the presence of plants can strongly affect the seasonal patterns of
460 treatment performance.

461 Few studies describe plankton communities in CWs (Chen et al., 2011; Luyiga and Kiwanuka,
462 2003; Li et al., 2014; Travaini-Lima et al., 2016), and none of them show results concerning
463 plankton reduction or production efficiencies in the way made here, therefore the comparison
464 with CWs in this respect from other sites in the world is difficult. On the other hand, artificial

465 aquatic food-web systems have been suggested as a promising approach for wastewater post
466 treatment, and as a cost-effective and sustainable technology (Guo et al., 2016; Lavrinovičs
467 and Juhna, 2017). Information obtained from the plankton community performance in our
468 CWs may be extremely useful in order to help with the design of artificial aquatic food-webs.

469 **4. Final remarks and conclusions**

470 Three CWs, with very different input water in terms of eutrophication, share similarities but
471 have many more clear differences in plankton performance related to eutrophication
472 remediation. Regarding similarities in plankton, over the two-year period each individual CW
473 received similar input waters, in terms of total phytoplankton and zooplankton biomass, but
474 unique for each one; there were no seasonal patterns in the case of phytoplankton and there
475 were peaks of cladocerans in spring in the three CWs, along with changes to larger body-sized
476 cladocerans within the systems, which are more effective at filtering microalgae. Moreover,
477 the three CWs reduced the cyanobacteria biomass. For the three CWs, the production
478 frequency of ostracods was greater in sectors B and A+B than in the systems as a whole.
479 With regard to differences, only TMCW improved the yield in phytoplankton removal over
480 time, and it also showed the highest phytoplankton removal frequencies; here, sector A
481 (horizontal subsurface flow CW) was really efficient because of the total dark conditions, along
482 with the interception mechanism inside the substrate, which were highly effective in
483 phytoplankton death and settling. The C sectors (the lagoons at the end of the system), played
484 a different role in each CW; TPCW being the one with the worst plankton performance. The
485 promotion and recovery of submerged vegetation in these lagoons is an imperative
486 management task. The seasonality of removal efficiencies is independent in each CW. For the
487 whole systems, 42 times more kg of DW phytoplankton was removed in TMCW compared to
488 TLICW, due to the much higher microalgal load in the inlet waters (7.8 times greater in TMCW),
489 the higher removal frequency, efficiency and rates, and the larger size of TMCW. TMCW
490 removed 55 and 34 times more cyanobacterial biomass than TPCW and TLICW, respectively.

491 Only TPCW reduced cryptophytes, the other two were producers of this algal group,
492 particularly TLICW. Only TLICW exported euglenophytes. TMCW was the only CW which
493 reduced copepod biomass, while TLICW was the only one that reduced the accumulate
494 biomass of rotifers.

495 We corroborate once more that in CWs, along with the physical, chemical and biological
496 processes of other organisms, the internal development of zooplankton largely contributes to
497 improve water quality through microalgal clearance, therefore it plays an important role in
498 eutrophication remediation. The proper development of vegetation, both emergent in the
499 primary sectors of the CWs, and submerged in the lagoons, is essential to achieve high removal
500 rates of phytoplankton and a high production of larger zooplankton. Both pigment
501 determinations and microalgal biovolume measurements should be integrated into the design
502 and management plans of CWs, particularly if there is a concern about changing algal
503 population dynamics and cyanobacteria and mixotrophic phytoplankton presence, as has been
504 demonstrated here. Therefore, we recommend incorporating a detailed study of the plankton
505 community in these plans, particularly for CWs included in protected environments.

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652

653

654 **Conflict of interest**

655 The authors declare there to be no conflict of interest.

656 **Author contributions**

657 MAR and MS conceived and designed the study. MAR and MS undertook the samplings, MS
658 did the taxonomical determination, counting of organisms and calculations. MAR wrote the
659 paper.

660

661

662 **Figure legends**

663 Fig. 1. Distribution of the mean percentage of phytoplankton (**A**) biovolume and zooplankton
664 biomass (**B**) in each year of the study period in the inlets, sector B and outlets of the three
665 CWs. The numbers above the bars indicate annual averages (\pm standard deviation) of
666 phytoplankton biovolume (in $\text{mm}^3 \text{L}^{-1}$) and zooplankton biomass (in $\mu\text{g DW L}^{-1}$) in each part of
667 the CWs.

668 Fig. 2. **A:** Relationships between concentrations of chlorophyll *a* and phytoplankton biovolume
669 in the three CWs. Equations are shown for each CW separately, and also considering the three
670 CWs together. The lower panel shows this relationship between values of chlorophyll lower
671 than $60 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ and of biovolume lower than $20 \text{mm}^3 \text{L}^{-1}$. **B:** Annual means in the three CWs of
672 the autotrophy/heterotrophy ratio which relate the biovolume of autotrophic groups (i.e.
673 Chlorophyceae and Bacillariophyceae) with the potential mixotrophic ones (i.e.
674 Cryptophyceae, Chrysophyceae, Dinophyceae and Euglenophyceae). Vertical thin bars are
675 standard deviations.

676 Fig. 3. Relationship between in vivo phycocyanin (measured as relative units of fluorescence,
677 RUF) and the cyanobacteria biovolume in the different sites of the three CWs.

678 Fig. 4. Cumulative mass reduction (Kg DW) in the two-year period of study (2014-2015) for the
679 main phytoplanktonic groups (cyanobacteria, diatoms, chlorophytes, cryptophytes and
680 euglenophytes) in the three constructed wetlands (TPCW, TMCM and TLICW). When the
681 removal series decreases, this implies that the last added value is of the opposite sign, then
682 net production occurs. Notice the difference in the scales of the y-axis for each CW and for
683 each phytoplanktonic group. Solid lines show data from the first sectors (B for TPCW and A+B
684 for the rest), and dashed lines represent global data for the whole CW (B+C for TPCW and
685 A+B+C for the rest). In the case of TPCW, data corresponding to the fp subsector are
686 distinguished from data from the FG subsector.

687 Fig. 5. Cumulative mass production (Kg DW) in the two-year period of study (2014-2015) for
688 the different zooplanktonic groups (cladocerans, ostracods, copepods and rotifers) in the three
689 constructed wetlands (TPCW, TMCM and TLICW). When the production series decreases this
690 implies than the last added value was of the opposite sign, then net loss occurs. Notice the
691 difference in the scales of the y-axis for each CW and for each zooplanktonic group. Solid lines
692 show data from the first sectors (B for TPCW and A+B for the rest), and dashed lines represent
693 global data for the whole CW (B+C for TPCW and A+B+C for the rest). In the case of TPCW, data
694 corresponding to the fp subsector are distinguished from data from the FG subsector.

Graphical Abstract

Highlights

Plankton removal and production in 3 constructed wetlands in a Natural Park are evaluated

Cumulative cyanobacterial mass reduction was 99, 163 and 5473 KgDW in the two-year period

Cladocerans and ostracods are very relevant for eutrophication reduction in the 3 CWs

Zooplankton production efficiencies were as high as 682%, 157% and 112% in the 3 CWs

Emergent and submerged plants largely help zooplankton production and microalgal removal

1 **PLANKTON PARTICIPATION IN THE PERFORMANCE OF THREE CONSTRUCTED**
2 **WETLANDS WITHIN A MEDITERRANEAN NATURAL PARK**

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7 **Abstract**

8 The contribution of plankton in the performance of three constructed wetlands (CWs) within
9 the Albufera de València Natural Park has been analyzed, taxonomic group by group, over a
10 two-year operation period in the different sectors of each CW: horizontal subsurface-flow –A–,
11 free-water surface –B– and lagoons –C–. Tancat de la Pipa CW (TPCW) only contains B-C
12 sectors, while the others have all three types. Treatment efficiency of each sector type on the
13 taxonomic groups was evaluated by calculating frequency of phytoplankton reduction
14 (zooplankton production), mass removal (production) efficiencies and rates, and accumulated
15 removed phytoplankton mass (produced zooplankton mass). The phytoplankton biomass
16 entering Tancat de Mília CW (TMCW) was significantly higher ($47 \pm 22 \text{ mm}^3 \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$) than in the other
17 CWs (10 ± 11 , $6 \pm 5 \text{ mm}^3 \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$), but the outlets did not show significant differences. 7574 and 180
18 kgDW were eliminated during the two-year period in TMCW and Tancat de L'illa CW (TLICW),
19 from which 72% and 91% were removed cyanobacteria. Conversely, 470 kgDW of
20 phytoplankton were produced in TPCW, but 99 kg of cyanobacteria eliminated. Mean
21 efficiencies in zooplankton production were 682%, 157% and 112% in TLICW, TMCW and
22 TPCW. There were evident spring production peaks of cladocerans in all CWs. Ostracods were
23 much more abundant in the B sectors (related to the high density of emergent vegetation). In
24 TMCW, the removal efficiencies were significantly higher during the second operation year.
25 These CWs have undergone changes in the composition of phytoplankton and zooplankton
26 communities, both spatially and temporally, which represent an improvement in the water

27 quality which is returned to the eutrophic main lagoon within the Natural Park. We do not
28 recommend using only chlorophyll and phycocyanin measurements as a surrogate of
29 phytoplankton and cyanobacterial biomass. Instead, this can be considered only as a
30 complement to the traditional analyses of microalgae and cyanobacterial presence.

31

32 **keywords:** Eutrophication remediation, Biological treatment, Phytoplankton, Zooplankton,
33 Cyanobacterial removal, Albufera de València lagoon

34

35 **1. Introduction**

36 Most wetlands are endangered worldwide by excessive nutrient contents caused by cultural
37 eutrophication (Verhoeven, 2014). This water deterioration compromises their ecosystem
38 services linked to biodiversity (Vymazal, 2011). The use of green infrastructures such as
39 constructed wetlands (CWs) located close to natural wetlands is nowadays growing, as an
40 effort to recover the lost services wetlands provide. CWs efficiently remove suspended
41 material, microalgae and nutrients from water (Chen et al., 2011; Dong et al., 2011; Travaini-
42 Lima et al., 2016). All this has as a consequence establishing better water conditions (increased
43 transparency, submerged vegetation recovery, etc.) and, therefore, enhanced biodiversity
44 occurs (Vymazal, 2011; Martín et al., 2013; Rodrigo et al., 2013a, b; Land et al., 2016).

45 Hernández-Crespo et al. (2017) have mainly analyzed the results on hydrology and physical
46 and chemical variables obtained from a two-year water quality monitoring program (2014-15)
47 in the frame of a “science-based governance” of CWs in the LIFE + 12 Albufera project. This
48 project is focused on demonstrating how three CWs can be managed, integrating multiple
49 objectives: (i) the reduction of pollutants from a hypereutrophic lagoon, l'Albufera de València,
50 a Ramsar and Natura 2000 site; (ii) the recovery of the lost habitats in the natural park it
51 belongs to, improving biodiversity both inside and outside the CWs, and (iii) for sustainable

52 and participatory public use. In the paper, it was reported how the results of the relationships
53 among hydraulic operation and physical and chemical variables in two different CWs
54 typologies (five free-water surface CW sectors and one horizontal subsurface flow CW sector)
55 show that the CWs were capable of improving the water quality, but showing clear differences
56 depending on the type of CW. One of these free-water surface CWs (Tancat de la Pipa -TPCW
57 hereafter-) has been operating and studied since 2009 (Martín et al., 2013; Rodrigo et al.,
58 2013a,b; Calero et al., 2015). As all of these authors and others (Li et al., 2014; Guo et al.,
59 2016) have already suggested, biological enhancement, in terms of zooplankton biomass
60 (particularly cladocerans), is a key variable in the restoration of eutrophic waters in these kinds
61 of systems. At the same time, clear shifts in phytoplankton composition towards a more
62 desirable community structure have already been observed in the waters of TPCW; for
63 example, the reduction of potentially toxic cyanobacteria (Rodrigo et al., 2013a). This time, the
64 study of three full scale CWs located relatively close to each other, influenced by similar but
65 not exactly the same factors, represents an invaluable opportunity to find similarities and
66 differences in plankton performance in order to detect patterns in the functioning of these
67 aquatic systems. Moreover, as already carried out for TPCW (Calero et al., 2017), we have
68 applied methods typically used only with nutrients when referring to CWs treatment
69 efficiencies to plankton variables, such as the calculation of cumulative mass removal and
70 production. Some studies have described plankton communities in CWs (Luyiga and Kiwanuka,
71 2003; Chen et al., 2011; Li et al., 2014; Travaini-Lima et al., 2016). However, none of them
72 show results concerning cumulative planktonic mass removal and production.

73 On occasion, photosynthetic pigments have been evaluated as a surrogate of phytoplankton
74 biomass (Kasprzak et al., 2008; Ramaraj et al., 2013) as simpler and more objective methods to
75 replace the traditional cell counting technique in natural waters, and for a reduction in
76 management costs. Recently, Canfield et al. (2019) concluded that if resources are limited,
77 chlorophyll is recommended for monitoring long-term trends in lakes because it provides an

78 estimate of biomass magnitude. Related to this, several studies have been published proposing
79 the measurement of *in vivo* phycocyanin (a photosynthetic accessory pigment) fluorescence as
80 an early warning or alert system for cyanobacteria presence especially in reservoir intake
81 waters (Ahn et al., 2007; Brient et al., 2008 and references therein). These methods have
82 proven to be appropriate under such circumstances. However, some questions can be posed:
83 are these methods suitable for other kinds of aquatic environments, for example wetlands, or,
84 as in this case, for CWs? Up to what limit (in terms of cyanobacteria biomass) might this
85 method be used in a reliable way?

86 Therefore, we have analyzed, in detail, the participation of plankton in the performance of
87 three CWs, and the specific objectives of this study are: (1) to analyze if chlorophyll *a* and *in*
88 *vivo* phycocyanin can be effectively used as a substitute for counting phytoplankton; (2) to
89 evaluate the removal frequencies, efficiencies and rates of phytoplankton; (3) to quantify the
90 production (or reduction) of the different zooplanktonic groups, and (4) to allow a comparison
91 of the different types of CWs and the different sectors within them in relation to the
92 contribution of plankton to eutrophication remediation.

93 **2. Material and methods**

94 *2.1. Study sites and CWs characteristics*

95 The study sites are three CWs, which were former rice fields, placed within the Albufera de
96 València Natural Park (Spain), a wetland of international importance (Hernández-Crespo et al.,
97 2017). It mainly consists of the Albufera de València lagoon, a hypereutrophic (current annual
98 mean chlorophyll *a* of approximately 100 µg L⁻¹) large lagoon (2,100 ha surface), surrounded
99 by 14,000 ha of fields devoted to rice cultivation. The Natural Park was subjected to high
100 urban, agricultural and industrial pressure. The three CWs are *Tancat de la Pipa*, 40 ha (TPCW
101 hereafter), *Tancat de Mília*, 33.4 ha (TMCW hereafter) and *Tancat de L'Illa*, 16 ha (TLICW
102 hereafter) (Fig. 1S). The three CWs have different combinations of free-water surface CWs
103 (sector B) and two of them have an area of horizontal subsurface flow CWs (sector A), and

104 operate at different hydraulic loads and water depths. The three CWs also have shallow
105 lagoons located at the end of the system (sector C). The incoming water, in the case of TPCW
106 and TMCW, is hypereutrophic water from the Albufera de València lagoon and, in the case of
107 TLICW, from a small lagoon that drains the irrigation water from the rice fields. After crossing
108 the CWs, the water is returned to the main lagoon. The water flows from the inlet to sectors A,
109 B and finally, C, except in TPCW, where there is no sector A. For further details on the study
110 sites see Hernández-Crespo et al. (2017).

111 *2.2. Sample collection and plankton determination*

112 Water samples were collected seasonally from January 2014 to December 2015: each year,
113 one sampling was performed in winter, three samplings in spring (March, April and May), as
114 this is the main season for the development of plankton in the Mediterranean region, one
115 sampling in summer (July) and one sampling in autumn (October). In each CW, four sampling
116 sites were chosen (the inlet, the outlet and two inner sites; Fig. 1S). In TPCW, sector B is
117 divided into two subsectors (fp and FG). Most samples were taken from the fp subsector, but
118 on a couple of occasions (July and October 2015) water samples were collected from the FG
119 subsector as the fp subsector had been dried for management reasons.

120 Unfiltered samples for phytoplankton counting were fixed with lugol and counted in Utermöhl
121 chambers with an inverted microscope (Olympus CK2) at 400 magnifications to obtain the
122 density. At least 400 individuals of the most abundant population were counted, implying a
123 10% error (Lund et al., 1958). Taxonomic determination was carried out using specific book
124 collections and reviews, such as *Archiv für Hydrobiologie (Algologische Studien)*, monographic
125 series of *Süßwasserflora von Mitteleuropa* (Gustav Fischer Verlag, Stuttgart) and *Das*
126 *Phytoplankton des Süßwassers* (Ed. Schweizerbart'sche Verlagsbuchhandlung) (more details in
127 Rojo et al., 2012). Algal biovolume was calculated with cell densities and cell volume,
128 measuring sizes from at least 20 individuals, and following Rott (1981) and Hillebrand et al.
129 (1999). For cumulative mass removal (see below), phytoplankton dry weight was obtained

130 from phytoplankton biovolume by assuming a cell density of 1 g cm^{-3} (Suthers et al., 2009) and
131 a wet/dry weight ratio of 10 (Chapra, 2008). Cumulative mass removal was expressed in
132 carbon units using the conversion of $\text{pg C cel}^{-1} = 0.216 \times \text{Biovol}(\mu\text{m}^3)^{0.939}$ for all microalgae
133 species, except for diatoms ($\text{pg C cel}^{-1} = 0.288 \times \text{Biovol}(\mu\text{m}^3)^{0.811}$) (Menden-Deuer and Lessard,
134 2000).

135 An autotrophy/mixotrophy ratio was calculated for each sampling date to relate the biovolume
136 of autotrophic groups (i.e. Chlorophyceae and Bacillariophyceae) with potential mixotrophic
137 ones (i.e. Cryptophyceae, Chrysophyceae, Dinophyceae and Euglenophyceae) (Rodrigo et al.,
138 2013a).

139 Water samples for metazooplankton were filtered through 45 mm Nylal mesh and preserved
140 with a formalin solution (at 4% final concentration). Density was calculated by counting with
141 an inverted microscope (Olympus CK2) at 100 magnifications. Taxonomic determination and
142 biomass were obtained following the methods described in Rojo et al. (2012); the manuals
143 used for the identification of metazooplankton taxa were those of Dussart (1967, 1969), Koste
144 (1978), Segers (1995), Einsle (1996), Orlova-Bienkowskaja (2001) and Nogrady and Segers
145 (2002). For biomass determination, at least 20 individuals of each population were measured.
146 Rotifer and ostracod biovolumes were calculated assimilating body shapes to geometrical
147 bodies. Biovolume was converted to biomass assuming a body density of 1 g cm^{-3} . Crustacean
148 biomass was obtained with length-dry weight regressions and a 1/10 proportion for dry wet
149 weight. The cumulative mass production was expressed in carbon units using the conversion 1
150 $\text{g DW} = 0.4 \text{ g C}$ for Rotifera, Cladocera and Copepoda (Reiss and Schmid-Araya, 2008).

151 2.3. Pigment determination

152 Water samples were also analyzed for chlorophyll *a*, which was determined after filtration
153 with glass microfiber filters (Whatman GF/F, pore size 0.7 μm) and extraction with 90%
154 acetone (Rodrigo et al., 2013a). *In situ* fluorescence measurements were performed with an
155 AquafluorTM handheld fluorometer (Turner designs) in each sampling site, equipped with two

156 channels. One of the channels was used for the excitation of phycocyanin pigments (excitation:
157 595 nm; emission: 670 nm). Water samples (around 3 ml) were placed in 10 mm x 10 mm
158 polystyrene cuvettes, and each sample was measured at 3-4 replicates. Calibration of the
159 device was carried out with two unialgal laboratory cultures (*Microcystis aeruginosa* and
160 *Spirulina* sp.). A phycocyanin extract (SigmaAldrich) was also used for calibration. For routine
161 measurements, single-point and blank type fluorometer calibration was used. Distilled water
162 was used as a blank. For the single-point, a solid secondary standard (P/N 8000-952) was used.
163 This allows quick and easy checks of calibration, stability and performance. The minimum
164 detection level of the instrument is about 150 cells mL⁻¹. Samples with high cyanobacteria
165 densities were diluted for phycocyanin measurements.

166 *2.4. Data analysis: correlation between pigments and phytoplankton biomass, removal-*
167 *production calculations and statistics*

168 Linear regression analyses were performed between photosynthetic pigments (chlorophyll *a*
169 and phycocyanin) and the biovolume of total phytoplankton and cyanobacteria, respectively,
170 for each CW.

171 The frequency of reduction of phytoplankton biomass comparing sector B (or A+B) and sector
172 C (or production of zooplankton) was calculated as the number of dates when this happens,
173 comparing the inlets and outlets divided by the total number of sampling dates (12). The
174 treatment efficiency of each of the above-mentioned sectors was determined from inlet total
175 plankton (and the different taxonomic groups) mass loading, annual mass removal efficiencies
176 (%), and mass removal rates (mg DW plankton m⁻² d⁻¹). The inflow (L s⁻¹), the input plankton
177 concentration (mg L⁻¹), the rainfall flow (L s⁻¹) which can exert a dilution effect, the
178 evapotranspiration (L s⁻¹) which can exert a concentration effect, the output plankton
179 concentration (mg L⁻¹) and the wetland area (m²) were considered. These variables were
180 considered constant between measurements, except for precipitation, since this is highly
181 variable in this area. After the two-year period of operation, the accumulated removed mass of

182 phytoplankton was calculated for sector B (or A+B) and the overall CW for each CW: the
183 difference between cumulative inflow and outflow. The cumulative inflow mass load was
184 estimated considering time between sampling dates (in days). For zooplankton, accumulated
185 produced mass was calculated, this being the difference between the cumulative outflow and
186 inflow. For more details about calculations see Hernández-Crespo et al. (2017).
187 Comparisons of means of the different plankton variables between the CWs, and between
188 sectors within each CW, were made with repeated ANOVA tests when normality and
189 homoscedasticity were accomplished. *Post hoc* Tukey's pairwise comparisons were performed
190 afterwards. Otherwise, non-parametric tests were used (Mann-Whitney two-samples). To
191 detect seasonality (intra-annual and interannual), Pearson (or Spearman) correlation
192 coefficients were determined between plankton variables. All statistical analyses were
193 executed using the statistical package IBM SPSS 19.0.

194 **3. Results and discussion**

195 *3.1. Planktonic biomass*

196 *3.1.1. Phytoplankton biomass*

197 The total phytoplankton two-year mean biomass entering TMCW was significantly higher ($47 \pm$
198 $22 \text{ mm}^3 \text{ L}^{-1}$) than in the other two CWs ($10 \pm 11 \text{ mm}^3 \text{ L}^{-1}$ in TPCW and $6 \pm 5 \text{ mm}^3 \text{ L}^{-1}$ in TLICW;
199 Fig. 1A, Table 1). This difference is explained by the different origins of incoming waters:
200 TMCW inputs are purely Albufera de València lagoon waters from its southern part, TPCW
201 inputs are also Albufera de València lagoon waters, but from the northern part and combined
202 with waters arriving at this lagoon through one channel and a gully which discharge upstream
203 waters, and finally TLICW is fed with water from a small lagoon that drains the irrigation water
204 from rice fields, with a much lower phytoplankton concentration. Only the cyanobacteria,
205 diatoms and chlorophyte biomass in the inlets was significantly higher in TMCW (Table 1S). In
206 spite of the higher total phytoplankton biomass in the TPCW outlet, the two-year annual
207 means were not statistically different among the three CWs. Only the biomass of

208 cyanobacteria was significantly higher in the TMCW outlet (mean of $2.2 \text{ mm}^3 \text{ L}^{-1}$) compared to
209 the outlets of TPCW and TLICW (means of 0.4 and $0.7 \text{ mm}^3 \text{ L}^{-1}$, respectively).

210 In the inlets of the three CWs, the total phytoplankton mean biomass was similar in the two
211 studied years (Fig. 1A; F_{ANOVA} and p-values in Table 1), and this also occurred with the different
212 taxonomic groups (Table 1S). The only exception was the mean cryptophyte biomass in the
213 TMCW inlet in 2015, which was half the mean of 2014. Overall, no repeated seasonal
214 dynamics, comparing 2014 and 2015, were found in any site in each of the CWs (see r_s and p-
215 values in Tables 1 and 1S). Only in the TMCW outlet was total phytoplankton significantly
216 lower in 2015, changing from a mean of 7 to $3 \text{ mm}^3 \text{ L}^{-1}$, and the cyanobacteria were
217 significantly reduced from 4 to $1 \text{ mm}^3 \text{ L}^{-1}$ from 2014 to 2015. However, some of the potentially
218 toxic cyanobacteria were found with slightly higher densities in 2015, but in no case were their
219 densities so high as to cause environmental or health problems. The low concentrations of
220 potential toxic cyanobacteria found during 2014-2015 in the three CWs are similar to the ones
221 found in the small lagoons (sector C) of TPCW in previous periods (Rodrigo et al., 2013a), and
222 they are below the toxicity limit of $2 \text{ mm}^3 \text{ L}^{-1}$ established for the Albufera de València lagoon
223 (Romo et al., 2013). Moreover, there was a clear relationship between cyanobacteria biomass
224 in the inlet and sector B in TPCW, which is not apparent in sector C (Table 1S). This significant
225 correlation was not found in TMCW or TLICW. In both cases, the presence of the subsurface
226 flow sector A, absent in TPCW, strongly modified the content of phytoplankton in sector B,
227 there being a weak relationship between the phytoplankton leaving sector A with the
228 phytoplankton in the inlet waters. TLICW had no significant differences in mean phytoplankton
229 biomass when comparing years, sites and seasonality. In other studies of the few considering
230 plankton performance in constructed wetlands (Chen et al., 2011), phytoplankton differed
231 significantly among but not within the different study wetlands.

232

233

234 3.1.2. Zooplankton biomass

235 The total zooplankton mean biomass entering TMCW was also significantly higher (290 ± 187
236 $\mu\text{g DW L}^{-1}$) than in the other two CWs ($124 \pm 101 \mu\text{g DW L}^{-1}$ in TPCW and $92 \pm 51 \mu\text{g DW L}^{-1}$ in
237 TLICW; Fig. 1B, F_{ANOVA} and p-values in Table 1). This difference was caused mainly by
238 cladocerans (Table 2S), indicating that the waters from the southern part of Albufera de
239 València lagoon are richer in this group. In the outlet, the zooplankton biomass was statistically
240 greater only in TLICW with respect to TPCW, in this case caused by the biomass of copepods.
241 Ostracod biomass was lower in TMCW compared to TPCW.

242 As happened with phytoplankton in the three CWs, the total zooplankton mean biomass (and
243 that of the taxonomic groups) in the inlet was similar in the two studied years (Fig. 1B; see
244 F_{ANOVA} and p-values, Tables 1 and 2S). However, the seasonal dynamics of total zooplankton
245 biomass was not the same in 2014 compared to 2015 in each of the CWs (r_s and p-values in
246 Table 1), with the exception of the cladoceran biomass in both the inlet and outlet of TMCW,
247 which showed significant correlations caused by peaks of this group during spring in both years
248 (Table 2S).

249 Similar to what happened with cyanobacteria in TPCW, there was a clear relationship between
250 total zooplankton biomass in the inlet and sector B of this CW (F_{ANOVA} and p-value, Table 1),
251 which did not occur in the outlets after the water had passed through sector C, and this
252 pattern was caused mainly by the copepod biomass (Table 2S). The change of cladoceran
253 biomass throughout this CW was more internal, not dependent on the inlet; the same
254 occurred with the ostracods (r_s and p-value in Table 2S). No correlation in total zooplankton
255 biomass was found between the different sites in TMCW or TLICW (Table 1), and the
256 explanation again can be found due to the existence of the subsurface flow in sector A.

257 In general terms, there was a seasonal replacement of zooplanktonic taxonomic groups
258 observed during this study in TPCW, typical of Mediterranean wetlands (copepod dominance
259 in winter interrupted by the spring bloom of cladocerans, and the dominance of rotifers in

260 summer and autumn; Rojo and Rodrigo, 2010). This pattern had been detected previously in
261 this CW (Rodrigo et al., 2013a; Calero et al., 2015) and it has now been confirmed for the other
262 two CWs. However, Travaini-Lima et al. (2016) found that rotifers were always the dominant
263 group in both the dry and wet seasons and sampling sites in tropical constructed wetlands but
264 copepods and cladocerans were more abundant during the rainy than during the dry season.
265 Chen et al. (2011) again found significant differences in zooplankton among but not within the
266 different study wetlands.

267 *3.2. Relationship between pigments and phytoplankton biomass*

268 The relationship between chlorophyll *a* and phytoplankton biovolume was statistically
269 significant in the three CWs (Fig. 2A). However, the relationship was different in TMCW, with a
270 much higher slope. Considering the same range of chlorophyll and biovolume for each CW (up
271 to $60 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ and $20 \text{mm}^3 \text{L}^{-1}$) where we find most of the data, most of the points corresponding
272 to TPCW are below the regression line, while the majority of the points of the other two CWs
273 are located above the line (Fig. 2A). This implies that the particular composition of
274 phytoplankton in each CWs yields a precise relationship of photosynthetic pigments and
275 microalgal biovolume, which is, in turn, related to the autotrophic or mixotrophic metabolism
276 of phytoplankton organism (Saad et al., 2016). The autotrophy/heterotrophy ratio was much
277 higher in the inlet, and also in the first part of sector B of TMCW, due to the high biomass of
278 cyanobacteria (Fig. 2B). Phycocyanin, the most common phycobilin in cyanobacteria of shallow
279 freshwaters (Stockner et al., 2000), was only significantly correlated with the biovolume of
280 cyanobacteria in the case of the higher values of both variables in the inlet of TMCW (Fig. 3).
281 On the other hand, the relationship of the pigment and the cyanobacteria biomass was
282 different in TPCW compared to TLICW: in the former, higher values of phycocyanin
283 corresponded to low biomasses, and in the latter, low values of the pigment corresponded to a
284 higher cyanobacterial biomass (Fig. 3). Again, depending on the particular composition of the
285 community, these relationships are clearly different. The type of cyanobacteria (unicellular,

286 colonial or filamentous organisms) and the real phycobilin composition (phycoerythrin-rich
287 cyanobacteria could also be present, Vörös et al., 2009), or even the presence of the other
288 phytoplankton group known to contain phycobiliproteins, i.e. cryptophytes (Downes and Hall,
289 1998), which were quite abundant in some samples of the CWs, might be the main causes of
290 the lack of a good correlation between the two kinds of determination carried out. Kasprzak et
291 al. (2008) and Ramaraj et al. (2013) recognized that chlorophyll is not an accurate
292 measurement of phytoplankton biomass. Therefore, we support this conclusion and we do not
293 recommend using only chlorophyll *a* and *in vivo* phycocyanin measurements as a surrogate of
294 phytoplankton and cyanobacterial biomass for CWs. Instead, they can be considered only as a
295 complement to the traditional analyses of microalgae and cyanobacterial presence. Therefore,
296 managers should integrate pigment determinations with microalgal biovolume measurements,
297 particularly if they are concerned about changing algal population dynamics and the presence
298 of cyanobacteria and mixotrophic phytoplankton.

299 *3.3. Phytoplankton removal frequencies, efficiencies and rates*

300 Removal frequencies, comparing the phytoplankton biomass in the inlets and the outlets, were
301 different among the CWs (Table 2): TMCW showed the highest frequency taking into account
302 the whole system, because in all the samplings the microalgal biomass at the outlet was lower
303 than at the inlet, and considering only sectors A+B the frequency was slightly lower; TPCW had
304 a removal frequency of 67% for the whole system, which was higher if only sector B was taken
305 into account; in TLICW, the frequency was the lowest, observing microalgal removal in only
306 50% of samplings, and there were no differences with regard to the whole system, or only in
307 sectors A+B. This means that sector C (the lagoons at the end of the system) played a different
308 role in each CW. In the case of TMCW, the lagoon improved removal efficiencies, in TPCW it
309 worsened them and in TLICW it had no effect. These differences might be related to the
310 presence of one island and several areas with emergent vegetation in the case of TMCW, so it
311 is less affected by wind resuspension; as for TPCW, in spite of it having two islands, the lower

312 hydraulic load rate and higher hydraulic retention time (Hernández-Crespo et al., 2017) must
313 have favored phytoplankton growth; the TLICW lagoon does not have any islands.

314 Regarding the reduction efficiencies of total phytoplankton, the two-year means in both TPCW
315 and TLICW were negative (Table 3) and statistically different from the positive mean of TMCW
316 (Table 4). In TPCW, only sector B had positive removal efficiencies. No seasonal correlation (r_s)
317 in reduction efficiencies among the CWs was found (Table 4). For the overall systems, the
318 mean reduction rate (Table 5) was maximal in TMCW ($74 \text{ mg DW m}^{-2}\text{d}^{-1}$) and minimum in
319 TPCW ($0.1 \text{ mg DW m}^{-2}\text{d}^{-1}$). In terms of cumulative mass reduction, 7574 kg DW and 180 kg DW
320 of phytoplankton were eliminated during the two-year period in TMCW and TLICW,
321 respectively, and, conversely, 470 kg DW of total phytoplankton were produced in TPCW.

322 Moreover, in none of the three CWs was a difference in the mean reduction efficiencies of
323 2014 compared to 2015 found. Only in TPCW was a seasonal pattern repeated each year, with
324 the production of total phytoplankton from the end of summer, autumn and winter, and a
325 reduction on the rest of the sampled dates, particularly in spring. The high nutrient
326 concentrations in water and sediment (Hernández-Crespo et al., 2017), together with the lack
327 of submerged vegetation in the small lagoons (sector C), the high temperatures in the warm
328 season and the elevated hours of sun in the geographic position of the site caused sector C to
329 act as a producer rather than a reducer of phytoplankton during this period.

330 Studying phytoplankton removal group by group, the frequency of cyanobacterial reduction
331 was 100% in TMCW and in sector B of TPCW. Only in TMCW were the removal efficiencies
332 significantly higher during the second year of operation (Table 2). Taking into account the two-
333 year period, cumulative cyanobacterial mass reduction was 99, 5473 and 163 Kg DW in TPCW,
334 TMCW and TLICW, respectively (Fig. 4) (~40, 1717 and 63 Kg C). The overall diatom reduction
335 frequency ranged from 75% (in TPCW and TLICW) to 92% (in TMCW). Removal shows similar
336 significant seasonal patterns in TPCW and TLICW (production in January, summer and autumn
337 2014 and a reduction in all seasons in 2015), but the mean reduction efficiency is statistically

338 higher in TMCW compared to TPCW and TLICW in sector B (or A+B). Cumulative diatom mass
339 reduction was 41, 1517 and 80 Kg DW in TPCW, TMCW and TLICW, respectively (~8, 140 and
340 13 Kg C). The overall chlorophyte reduction frequency was as low as 33% in TPCW and 100% in
341 TMCW, and the mean removal efficiency was positive only in TMCW, and therefore
342 significantly higher. No seasonality between each CWs was observed, but, again, there was a
343 significantly higher reduction in chlorophytes in TMCW during the second year of operation.
344 Cumulative chlorophyte mass reduction was 570 Kg DW (~205 Kg C) in TMCW, and 2 and 22 Kg
345 were produced in TPCW and TLICW, respectively. Only TPCW showed cryptophyte reduction
346 frequencies higher than 80% considering all sectors, and it was the only CW to generate
347 positive removal efficiencies; cryptophyte production was statistically much higher in TLICW
348 (Table 2). Cumulative cryptophyte mass reduction was 6 Kg DW in TPCW, with a cumulative
349 mass production of 77 and 866 Kg DW in TMCW and TLICW, respectively. Finally,
350 euglenophytes had negative reduction efficiencies in the three CWs (Table 3S) with no
351 statistical differences (Table 4S), but the mean reduction rates were positive, although close to
352 0 in TPCW and TMCW; seasonality was only observed between TPCW and TMCW (they had
353 large production peaks mainly at the same time, summer 2014 and autumn 2015). In terms of
354 cumulative reduction or production for the two-year period, 1 and 28 kg DW were reduced in
355 TPCW and TMCW, respectively, but 51 Kg DW were produced in TLICW (Fig. 4).
356 TMCW and TLICW were created shortly before the monitoring included in this study, therefore
357 it is not possible to compare them with the previous situation, unlike TPCW which was created
358 in 2008, with monitoring starting in 2009. The removal rate of total phytoplankton in sector B
359 in TPCW in 2014-2015 is much lower ($40 \text{ mg m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$) than that found during the first year of
360 operation ($151 \text{ mg m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$; Calero et al., 2015), but much higher than for the second and third
361 years of operation, when the rates were negative (-26 and $-47 \text{ mg m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$; Calero et al., 2015).
362 Macrophytes in CWs have a strong influence on the structure and dynamics of the

363 phytoplankton community, since their coverage is a major factor strongly modifying light
364 conditions (Travaini-Lima et al., 2016). During the first year, the coverage of emergent
365 vegetation (mainly *Typha* spp.) was extensive, but it was harvested. The recovery of vegetation
366 was not as successful as expected, and this is why later rates were negative. However, in the
367 new period, vegetation was recovered (this time mainly with *Phragmites australis*) and the
368 removal rates increased again.

369 3.4. Zooplankton production frequencies, efficiencies and rates

370 In the overall systems, the production frequency of total zooplankton (Table 2) was maximum
371 in TLICW and minimum in TMCW. Regarding production efficiencies (Table 3), and in spite of
372 the two-year mean value of TLICW being much higher (682%) than the other two CWs (112%
373 and 157%), there were no statistical differences among them due to the large variability in
374 each studied date. No seasonal pattern between the three CWs was found, nor was there a
375 seasonal pattern in each CW between years (Table 4).

376 Studying zooplankton production group by group, in the case of cladocerans the production
377 frequency (Table 2) was not very different among the CWs, but the mean efficiencies were
378 much higher in TLICW (Table 5S); however, due to the high production on particular dates, the
379 differences were not statistically significant (Table 6S). Moreover, there was a clear significant
380 seasonality in the production of cladocerans in the three CWs, with the maxima in April (r_s ,
381 Table 6S). Every year in the spring, large blooms of cladocerans produce plentiful amounts of
382 resting eggs which enrich the sediment bank to densities as high as 2.8 ± 0.3 ephippia cm^{-2} for
383 example in TPCW (unpublished results), waiting for hatching in the next spring
384 (Vandekerkhove et al., 2005). In sector B (or A+B) the mean production rates varied between a
385 minimum of $0.8 \text{ mg DW m}^{-2}\text{d}^{-1}$ for TLICW and a maximum of $4 \text{ mg DW m}^{-2}\text{d}^{-1}$ in TMCW (Table
386 8S); here, cumulative production reached 185 Kg DW at the end of sector C up to spring 2015
387 (Fig. 5). This accounted for 74 Kg of carbon produced internally in the system. In TLICW, the
388 production of cladocerans in sector C was high from spring of the second study year (more

389 than 230 Kg DW; 92 Kg of C). In TMCW, the increase in cladocerans was related with the higher
390 density of edible microalgae which substituted the cyanobacteria. Overall, the three CWs
391 received waters with smaller-size cladocerans and produced internally larger-size species with
392 greater grazing capacity (e.g. in TPCW *Chydorus sphaericus* in the inlet was substituted by
393 *Daphnia magna* in sector B; in the TMCW inlet *Moina micrura* and *Diaphanosoma*
394 *mongolianum* were substituted by *Ceriodaphnia reticulata* and several species of *Daphnia* (*D.*
395 *magna* represented more than 90% of biomass in spring 2015); in TLICW *D. magna* and *C.*
396 *reticulata* were exported from the system. This fact supports the observations of Guo et al.
397 (2016) who stressed how artificial aquatic food web systems not only efficiently removed
398 nutrients from sewage waters, but also increased the P-absorbance of *Daphnia*.

399 The production frequency of ostracods was higher in sectors B and A+B compared to the
400 system as a whole in the three CWs (Table 2). Ostracods were produced in the three CWs with
401 high mean efficiencies (Table 5S). In the fp subsector (sector B), a cumulative biomass of 55 Kg
402 DW of ostracods was produced at the end of the two-year study (Fig. 5). In the FG subsector
403 (sector B), the value was much lower, but in this case the data series is much shorter, these
404 results not being comparable. More than 20 Kg DW of cumulative biomass of ostracods in
405 sector B in TMCW were produced (Fig. 5). The increase in this group, mainly of benthic
406 features (Schmit et al., 2007), particularly in the B sectors, is clearly related to the type of
407 environment these sites provide: a high density of emergent vegetation compared to the C
408 sectors (lagoons) (Rodrigo et al., 2013a; Hernández-Crespo et al., 2017), therefore there is a
409 much greater surface for these organisms to live on, which may be carried along by the water
410 flow and hence be susceptible to being sampled at the outlets. This group has experienced an
411 important loss of biodiversity in western Mediterranean wetlands due to eutrophication and
412 pollution problems (Poquet et al., 2008; Valls et al., 2016); therefore, the development of this
413 group inside the CWs could help to turn this situation back to what it previously was.

414 The copepod production frequency for sectors A+B+C of TMCW was 0, which contrasts with
415 67% for the other two CWs (Table 2). Production efficiencies in this CW were statistically
416 different in comparison to the other two CWs (Tables 5S and 6S) because this group's biomass
417 is reduced rather than being increased. The removal of copepods in TMCW yielded an
418 accumulated value of 153 Kg DW for the two-year study, and the cumulative production of
419 copepods for TPCW and TLICW was 3 and 49 Kg DW, respectively. In the case of rotifers, the
420 production frequencies were the same for TPCW and TMCW for the whole system, but lower
421 than for TLICW (Table 2). Seasonality in the reduction efficiencies of both TMCW and TLICW
422 was observed over the two years, but the pattern was different among CWs. In TMCW, there
423 were clear production periods only in summer and at the beginning of autumn. In TLICW, there
424 were production peaks in March in both years; but in the second year the production peak in
425 summer was not observed. In the latter CW, rotifers were removed from the whole system by
426 7 Kg DW of cumulative mass (2.8 Kg C). Overall, a reduction in rotifers, rather than production,
427 might be interpreted as an improvement in water quality (Lodi et al., 2011; Jurczak et al.,
428 2019).

429 Most of the differences in zooplankton performance between sectors B and C are due to the
430 existence of emergent vegetation in the case of sectors B, versus open water practically
431 without submerged vegetation in the lagoons of the three CWs. On the other hand, the
432 differences between B sectors might be related to the type of emergent vegetation planted in
433 each case (Travaini-Lima et al., 2016). In TPCW, emergent plants existing in sector B were
434 mixed populations of *Phragmites australis*, *Typha angustifolia*, *Sparganium erectum* and *Iris*
435 *pseudacorus*, whereas in TMCW and TLICW they were mainly *Typha angustifolia*. Also, the
436 coverage of emergent vegetation was greater in TLICW (Hernández-Crespo et al., 2018).
437 Rodrigo et al. (2018) reported how the type of emergent vegetation (and its coverage)
438 influences the eutrophication reduction effect. The different kinds of emergent plants could

439 provide different surfaces onto which zooplankton diapausing eggs could be attached
440 (Gyllstrom and Hansson, 2004).

441 TPCW increased the percentage of production efficiencies of zooplankton in comparison to
442 previous studies (2009-2012), increasing from mean values of 65% in subsector FG of sector B
443 (Calero et al., 2015) or 75% in sector C (Rodrigo et al., 2013a) to more than 100%, both in the
444 CW as a whole, and in sector C. The mean production rate of total zooplankton in sector B (fp
445 subsector) in TPCW is slightly higher ($34 \text{ mg DW m}^{-2}\text{d}^{-1}$) than the one estimated for this sector
446 ($27 \text{ mg DW m}^{-2}\text{d}^{-1}$) in 2009-2012 (Calero et al., 2015). However, the large difference is due to
447 the highest production being in ostracod and copepod biomass, rather than the biomass of
448 cladocerans, which occurred in the previous period. Thus, the large grazers, the cladocerans,
449 have been partially substituted by the ostracods, which are also herbivores and detritivores, in
450 the role of the reduction of microalgae biomass. The aging of this CW resulted in important
451 changes in the zooplankton community structure. On the other hand, the comparison of
452 zooplankton between the inlet and the outlet of sector C (the lagoons) indicates a lower
453 production rate than that calculated for 2009-2012 ($2 \text{ mg DW m}^{-2}\text{d}^{-1}$; Rodrigo et al., 2013a). For
454 most of that period, the lagoon was characterized as possessing a wide coverage of submerged
455 vegetation, mainly *Myriophyllum spicatum* (Rodrigo et al., 2013b) but this disappeared in 2011
456 and despite efforts to recover it, this coverage never occurred again. The presence of this
457 vegetation clearly contributed to the development of large cladocerans, which could be hidden
458 from their predators within the submerged macrophytes (Burks et al., 2001). As stated by
459 Dong et al. (2011), the presence of plants can strongly affect the seasonal patterns of
460 treatment performance.

461 Few studies describe plankton communities in CWs (Chen et al., 2011; Luyiga and Kiwanuka,
462 2003; Li et al., 2014; Travaini-Lima et al., 2016), and none of them show results concerning
463 plankton reduction or production efficiencies in the way made here, therefore the comparison
464 with CWs in this respect from other sites in the world is difficult. On the other hand, artificial

465 aquatic food-web systems have been suggested as a promising approach for wastewater post
466 treatment, and as a cost-effective and sustainable technology (Guo et al., 2016; Lavrinovičs
467 and Juhna, 2017). Information obtained from the plankton community performance in our
468 CWs may be extremely useful in order to help with the design of artificial aquatic food-webs.

469 **4. Final remarks and conclusions**

470 Three CWs, with very different input water in terms of eutrophication, share similarities but
471 have many more clear differences in plankton performance related to eutrophication
472 remediation. Regarding similarities in plankton, over the two-year period each individual CW
473 received similar input waters, in terms of total phytoplankton and zooplankton biomass, but
474 unique for each one; there were no seasonal patterns in the case of phytoplankton and there
475 were peaks of cladocerans in spring in the three CWs, along with changes to larger body-sized
476 cladocerans within the systems, which are more effective at filtering microalgae. Moreover,
477 the three CWs reduced the cyanobacteria biomass. For the three CWs, the production
478 frequency of ostracods was greater in sectors B and A+B than in the systems as a whole.
479 With regard to differences, only TMCW improved the yield in phytoplankton removal over
480 time, and it also showed the highest phytoplankton removal frequencies; here, sector A
481 (horizontal subsurface flow CW) was really efficient because of the total dark conditions, along
482 with the interception mechanism inside the substrate, which were highly effective in
483 phytoplankton death and settling. The C sectors (the lagoons at the end of the system), played
484 a different role in each CW; TPCW being the one with the worst plankton performance. The
485 promotion and recovery of submerged vegetation in these lagoons is an imperative
486 management task. The seasonality of removal efficiencies is independent in each CW. For the
487 whole systems, 42 times more kg of DW phytoplankton was removed in TMCW compared to
488 TLICW, due to the much higher microalgal load in the inlet waters (7.8 times greater in TMCW),
489 the higher removal frequency, efficiency and rates, and the larger size of TMCW. TMCW
490 removed 55 and 34 times more cyanobacterial biomass than TPCW and TLICW, respectively.

491 Only TPCW reduced cryptophytes, the other two were producers of this algal group,
492 particularly TLICW. Only TLICW exported euglenophytes. TMCW was the only CW which
493 reduced copepod biomass, while TLICW was the only one that reduced the accumulate
494 biomass of rotifers.

495 We corroborate once more that in CWs, along with the physical, chemical and biological
496 processes of other organisms, the internal development of zooplankton largely contributes to
497 improve water quality through microalgal clearance, therefore it plays an important role in
498 eutrophication remediation. The proper development of vegetation, both emergent in the
499 primary sectors of the CWs, and submerged in the lagoons, is essential to achieve high removal
500 rates of phytoplankton and a high production of larger zooplankton. Both pigment
501 determinations and microalgal biovolume measurements should be integrated into the design
502 and management plans of CWs, particularly if there is a concern about changing algal
503 population dynamics and cyanobacteria and mixotrophic phytoplankton presence, as has been
504 demonstrated here. Therefore, we recommend incorporating a detailed study of the plankton
505 community in these plans, particularly for CWs included in protected environments.

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654 **Conflict of interest**

655 The authors declare there to be no conflict of interest.

656 **Author contributions**

657 MAR and MS conceived and designed the study. MAR and MS undertook the samplings, MS
658 did the taxonomical determination, counting of organisms and calculations. MAR wrote the
659 paper.

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661

662 **Figure legends**

663 Fig. 1. Distribution of the mean percentage of phytoplankton (**A**) biovolume and zooplankton
664 biomass (**B**) in each year of the study period in the inlets, sector B and outlets of the three
665 CWs. The numbers above the bars indicate annual averages (\pm standard deviation) of
666 phytoplankton biovolume (in $\text{mm}^3 \text{L}^{-1}$) and zooplankton biomass (in $\mu\text{g DW L}^{-1}$) in each part of
667 the CWs.

668 Fig. 2. **A:** Relationships between concentrations of chlorophyll *a* and phytoplankton biovolume
669 in the three CWs. Equations are shown for each CW separately, and also considering the three
670 CWs together. The lower panel shows this relationship between values of chlorophyll lower
671 than $60 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ and of biovolume lower than $20 \text{mm}^3 \text{L}^{-1}$. **B:** Annual means in the three CWs of
672 the autotrophy/heterotrophy ratio which relate the biovolume of autotrophic groups (i.e.
673 Chlorophyceae and Bacillariophyceae) with the potential mixotrophic ones (i.e.
674 Cryptophyceae, Chrysophyceae, Dinophyceae and Euglenophyceae). Vertical thin bars are
675 standard deviations.

676 Fig. 3. Relationship between in vivo phycocyanin (measured as relative units of fluorescence,
677 RUF) and the cyanobacteria biovolume in the different sites of the three CWs.

678 Fig. 4. Cumulative mass reduction (Kg DW) in the two-year period of study (2014-2015) for the
679 main phytoplanktonic groups (cyanobacteria, diatoms, chlorophytes, cryptophytes and
680 euglenophytes) in the three constructed wetlands (TPCW, TMCM and TLICW). When the
681 removal series decreases, this implies that the last added value is of the opposite sign, then
682 net production occurs. Notice the difference in the scales of the y-axis for each CW and for
683 each phytoplanktonic group. Solid lines show data from the first sectors (B for TPCW and A+B
684 for the rest), and dashed lines represent global data for the whole CW (B+C for TPCW and
685 A+B+C for the rest). In the case of TPCW, data corresponding to the fp subsector are
686 distinguished from data from the FG subsector.

687 Fig. 5. Cumulative mass production (Kg DW) in the two-year period of study (2014-2015) for
688 the different zooplanktonic groups (cladocerans, ostracods, copepods and rotifers) in the three
689 constructed wetlands (TPCW, TMCM and TLICW). When the production series decreases this
690 implies than the last added value was of the opposite sign, then net loss occurs. Notice the
691 difference in the scales of the y-axis for each CW and for each zooplanktonic group. Solid lines
692 show data from the first sectors (B for TPCW and A+B for the rest), and dashed lines represent
693 global data for the whole CW (B+C for TPCW and A+B+C for the rest). In the case of TPCW, data
694 corresponding to the fp subsector are distinguished from data from the FG subsector.

Table 1

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Table 1. Significant results of repeated measures ANOVA tests (F and p-value) and *post hoc* Tukey's pairwise comparisons, or two-sample Mann-Whitney tests when criteria for ANOVA were not met, for total phytoplankton biovolume and total zooplankton biomass, comparing between years and between sites within each CW, and between CWs. The arrows indicate if the biovolume or biomass means increased (\uparrow) in the second "item" of comparison, or decreased (\downarrow) (e.g. TPCW vs TMCW \uparrow : the mean biovolume or biomass is higher in TMCW). Spearman correlation coefficients (and p-value) to detect seasonality in the phytoplankton biovolume and zooplankton biomass within each CW comparing 2014 and 2015 values, and between CWs in the two-year data series. n.s.: non-statistically significant. vs: *versus*. Results for the taxonomic groups are shown in Supplementary Materials (Tables 1S and 2S).

	Total Phytoplank.				Total Zooplank.			
	F/Q	p	r_s	p	F/Q	p	r_s	p
TPCW								
Two-year period								
P3 vs P5	n.s.		0.69	0.013	n.s.		0.80	0.002
P5 vs P6	n.s.		0.77	0.003	n.s.		0.88	0.001
P3 vs P6	n.s.			n.s.	n.s.		0.87	<0.001
TMCW								
2014 vs 2015								
Outlet (P8)	\downarrow 17.7	0.008	0.94	0.003	n.s.			n.s.
Two-year period								
P1 vs P5	\downarrow 11.9	<0.001		n.s.	n.s.			n.s.
P5 vs P6		n.s.	0.67	0.017	n.s.			n.s.
P1 vs P6	\downarrow 12.2	<0.001		n.s.	\downarrow 5.2	0.043		n.s.
P6 vs P8		n.s.	0.67	0.017	n.s.			n.s.
P1 vs P8	\downarrow 12.2	<0.001		n.s.	n.s.			n.s.
TLICW								
2014 vs 2015								
Sect. B (P7)		n.s.		n.s.	n.s.		0.89	0.017
Two-year period								
P1 vs P8		n.s.		n.s.	\uparrow 5.1	0.045		n.s.
INLETS (two-year period)								
TPCW vs TMCW	\uparrow 8.5	<0.001		n.s.	\uparrow 7.3	0.021		n.s.
TLICW vs TMCW	\uparrow 9.5	<0.001		n.s.	\uparrow 16.7	0.002		n.s.
OUTLETS (two-year period)								
TPCW vs TLICW		n.s.		n.s.	\uparrow 4.7	0.053	0.71	0.001

Table 2[Click here to download Table: Table 2.docx](#)

Table 2. Reduction frequency of total phytoplankton biomass and its taxonomic groups, and production frequency of total zooplankton biomass and its taxonomic groups, for the two-year data series in the different sectors of the three CWs.

		Frequency of reduction (%)				
	Total Phytopl.	Cyanobac.	Diatoms	Chloroph.	Cryptoph.	Euglenoph.
TPCW						
Sector B	75	100	75	58	67	50
Sectors B+C	67	67	75	33	83	67
TMCW						
Sectors A+B	92	100	92	83	50	40
Sectors A+B+C	100	100	92	100	58	40
TLICW						
Sectors A+B	50	83	83	75	50	45
Sectors A+B+C	50	67	75	50	0	33
		Frequency of production (%)				
	Total Zoopl.	Cladoc.	Ostrac.	Copep.	Rotifers	
TPCW						
Sector B	67	64	91	58	58	
Sectors B+C	50	50	67	67	33	
TMCW						
Sectors A+B	25	17	90	17	25	
Sectors A+B+C	33	42	56	0	33	
TLICW						
Sectors A+B	58	33	64	42	58	
Sectors A+B+C	67	58	50	67	42	

Table 3

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Table 3. Mean (\pm standard deviation) reduction efficiencies (%) for total phytoplankton biomass and production efficiencies (%) for total zooplankton biomass, in the different sectors of the three CWs taking into account the two-year period. In the case of TPCWs, data for the two different subsectors (fp and FG) are shown. For phytoplankton, negative percentage signs indicate production instead of reduction (expressed in italics). For zooplankton, negative percentage signs indicate reduction instead of production (expressed also in italics). Results for the taxonomic groups are shown in Supplementary Materials (Tables 3S and 4S).

		Two-year mean (\pm SD) reduction* or production** efficiencies (%)	
		Total Phytoplankton*	Total Zooplankton**
TPCW			
P5 vs P6	fp	24 \pm 38	13 \pm 57
	FG	-24 \pm 98	9 \pm 16
Sector B (P3 vs P6)	fp	10 \pm 70	34 \pm 98
	FG	73 \pm 0	5 \pm 7
Sectors B+C (P3 vs P8)		-167 \pm 447	-0.2 \pm 1
TMCW			
P5 vs P6		24 \pm 103	8 \pm 46
Sectors A+B (P1 vs P6)		84 \pm 29	6 \pm 8
Sectors A+B+C (P1 vs P8)		87 \pm 13	0.4 \pm 10
TLICW			
P5 vs P7		-94 \pm 187	20 \pm 58
Sector A+B (P1 vs P7)		-56 \pm 153	8 \pm 20
Sectors A+B+C (P1 vs P8)		-118 \pm 314	-5 \pm 9

Table 4[Click here to download Table: Table 4.docx](#)

Table 4. Significant results of statistical analyses comparing the means in the reduction efficiencies of total phytoplankton and in the production efficiencies of total zooplankton (U and p-values) between the two-year period of operation, and within each CW, and between CWs in Sector B (or A+B depending on the CWs) and in Sectors B+C (or A+B+C). Arrows' meaning as in Table 1. Spearman correlation coefficients (and p-value) to detect seasonality in the reduction efficiency of phytoplankton and production efficiency of zooplankton within each CW comparing 2014 and 2015 values, and between CWs in the two-year data series. n.s.: non statistically significant. For TMCW and TLICW, no statistically significant results comparing 2014 vs 2015 were obtained. Results for the taxonomic groups are shown in Supplementary Materials (Tables 3S and 5S)

	Total Phytoplankton				Total Zooplankton			
	U	p	r _s	p	U	p	r _s	p
2014 vs 2015								
TPCW								
Sectors B+C		n.s.	0.83	0.033		n.s.		n.s.
Two-year period								
SECTOR B or A+B								
TPCW vs TMCW	↑16	0.005		n.s.		n.s.		n.s.
TLICW vs TMCW	↑10	<0.001		n.s.		n.s.		n.s.
TPCW vs TLICW		n.s.		n.s.		n.s.	0.59	0.042
SECTOR B+C or A+B+C								
TPCW vs TMCW	↑34	0.030		n.s.		n.s.		n.s.
TLICW vs TMCW	↑8	<0.001		n.s.		n.s.		n.s.

Table 5

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Table 5. Mean (\pm standard deviation) reduction rates for total phytoplankton biomass and production rates for total zooplankton biomass, in the different sectors of the three CWs taking into account the two-year period. In the case of TPCW, data for the two different subsectors (fp and FG) are shown. For phytoplankton, negative rate signs indicate production rather than reduction (expressed in italics). For zooplankton, negative percentage signs indicate reduction rather than production (expressed also in italics). Results for the taxonomic groups are shown in Supplementary Materials (Tables 7S and 8S).

			Two-year mean (\pm SD) of reduction* or production** rates (mg DW/m² d)	
			Total Phytoplankton*	Total Zooplankton**
TPCW				
P5 vs P6	fp		50 \pm 83	13 \pm 57
	FG		21 \pm 35	9 \pm 16
Sector B (P3 vs P6)	fp		40 \pm 71	34 \pm 98
	FG		30 \pm 33	5 \pm 7
Sectors B+C (P3 vs P8)			0.1 \pm 25	-0.2 \pm 1
TMCW				
P5 vs P6			11 \pm 44	8 \pm 46
Sectors A+B (P1 vs P6)			140 \pm 93	6 \pm 8
Sectors A+B+C (P1 vs P8)			74 \pm 46	0.4 \pm 10
TLICW				
P5 vs P7			-7 \pm 36	20 \pm 58
Sectors A+B (P1 vs P7)			6 \pm 20	8 \pm 20
Sectors A+B+C (P1 vs P8)			3 \pm 12	-5 \pm 9

Fig. 1

2 columns

Fig. 2 (A and B)

2 columns

Fig. 3

1.5 columns

Fig. 4

2 columns

Fig. 5

2 columns

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